

**THE PROGRAM OF APPLYING NEW PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH AND
PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY AT SCHOOL**

O'telbayeva Muhayyo Alisherovna
Chemistry teacher at school

Abstract: School chemical experiment to students is an important method of acquiring scientific knowledge. Teaching and explaining chemical processes through joint learning and experimentation is important for the teacher. Teacher plays an important role in improving students' scientific literacy. However, the available chemical some problems may arise during experimental teaching in elementary school. for example, lack of reactants needed for a chemical reaction. These problems hinder the scientific study of elementary school. This study analyzes the advantages of the chemical experiment teaching mode and new research-based methods of explaining chemical reaction processes to the student will be considered from a cooperative learning perspective. Based on chemical principles and in terms of collaborative learning, this study suggests that experiential learning is a new methods of cooperative teaching for elementary school chemistry experiments are presented. Cooperative learning situations for elementary school chemistry, so learn how helps to increase the scientific literacy of students and increase their interest in chemistry. For this, the teacher will need to apply pedagogical and psychological knowledge and research.

Keywords: Learning chemistry in the laboratory, chemical experiments, teaching model, science chemistry in elementary school, pedagogical skills, psychological approaches.

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Introduction

A chemical experiment is the main way to study and study a material is to change it. Demonstration of chemical experiments plays an important role for students to understand chemistry in school. It is necessary to develop the main achievements of students in chemistry and to explain the content and essence of chemistry to students. Arousing and gaining students' interest the use of chemical experiments in the study of chemistry and it can create visual learning situations. At school, it will be necessary to help students to understand and master chemical knowledge and skills, pedagogical knowledge and psychological approaches will be needed from the teacher. For this, it is necessary to teach students scientific methods, to explain scientific attitudes and approaches in students. However, cooperative awareness is currently weak and its role in primary classes is not clear several problems may arise in the experimental teaching of chemistry at school. The individual difference of schoolchildren is clear, the class balance is difficult; The topics discussed in the group are not aggregated and scientific understanding not clear. To solve existing problems in experimental teaching of chemistry in elementary grades it is necessary to innovate the existing cooperative education model in schools. At the same time, the student should follow the experimental work during chemistry. Experimental teaching of chemistry in elementary schools has the characteristics of a

cooperative it is necessary to apply learning and waiting methods. First, classroom inquiry activities are designed according to academic research and the model of social cooperation of scholars and the academic tasks of elementary school learners are promoted through social interpersonal relationships. Second, through formation study groups, close and interdependent relationships are built in which individuals interact and with other individuals or groups around and using each other's resources and skills can be shared. Ask each other for information, evaluate each other's opinion, monitor each other, work and other strategies, each person's learning effect can be optimized, and then overall academic goals can be achieved. Finally, cooperative learning has a solid theoretical foundation. To improve pedagogical and psychological skills I think it is necessary to study philosophy, sociology and psychology. Its advantages lie in two visible integrations and provides a variety of goals, academic learning and interpersonal communication. Performs a variety of training and guides the achievement of goals through the learning process. **Experiential Task Specific Requirement:** Muhayyo believes in good collaborative learning and tasks require high intelligence, strong creativity and open results. **Experimental selection** In experimental projects, the context should be compatible with the requirement of good cooperation. Learning tasks through problem setting and collaborative learning in real environments, it is necessary to find a way to solve the problem and achieve the educational goal. Each student should be given memorable information about chemistry during the lesson.

Emphasis on problem solving and developing students' ways of thinking in chemistry teaching

The main purpose of experimental teaching of chemistry in school is to improve students' understanding and is to better explain scientific laws through experiments. For this, first of all, the mode of experimental training based on cooperative learning helps to develop scientific thinking. students can supplement what they have learned and can accomplish challenging tasks together through cooperative learning through active participation. It can change learning responsibilities to students in the classroom, which students define and decide to accomplish. Rather than copying and pasting problems to provide teachers and textbooks in their own words can share information from the material with each other. Students in the class talk more and ask more questions than students who are not in it. Students try to explain their understanding of the topic. Understanding the content of chemistry is a means of effective strengthening of scientific information communication. When students actively participate in the learning environment and share ideas, students are truly engaged learning process, they control their own learning, which has a direct positive effect and stimulate students' learning motivation, affect learning time and learning, we can see good learning outcomes. Therefore, students' inclination towards science increases. When team members have disagreements about cooperation, they act the conflict in your mind needs to be resolved through deeper reflection and adjustment and they begin to think to understand problems. Thus, it forms, strengthens and strengthens scientific thinking at a higher level scientific concepts of critical thinking, improving understanding of science, helping to further develop strategies for solving scientific problems, strengthening students' continuous attention to chemistry, creates opportunities for students' future success.

Picture 1. An experimental mode of teaching chemistry based on cooperative learning.

Method of experimental teaching process

The main goal of this educational method is for students to work under the guidance of teachers. Enriching their knowledge and concepts, to improve the ability to conduct scientific experiments, to increase their interests it is necessary to conduct scientific experimental courses. First of all, this experiment should combine scientific experience and artistic practical painting, involves some complex operational steps. The project has certain difficulties, so it needs it is necessary to have a high level of leadership and pedagogical potential of teachers. One of them is that the students understood and participated before this lesson group cooperative learning and the teacher gives appropriate explanations of the basic skills, team management, communication and conflict resolution will be required. Second, before officially starting experiment, the teacher explains the cooperative learning mode and the meaning of this lesson and emphasizes group goals, individual responsibilities, evaluation methods, and other content. Thirdly, the teacher conducted an experiment in advance, eliminated the possible danger of the laboratory and ensures the safety of the experiment, strengthened the students' knowledge of laboratory safety and develops the ability to cope with danger. Second, doing good work in the form of group division it is necessary to provide brief information about the work and project content within the group division of labor. In terms of the division of labor outside group, the teacher divides the class into six groups according to the knowledge base, operative it increases the ability and interest of the students. In terms of division of labor within the group, based on the requirements of various tasks such as general planning, information regulation experimental operation, safety guarantee, environmental protection, etc., arranged by the teacher different roles for each member of the group, such as group leader, information collector, experimental operator, safety assurance officer, environmental protection supervisor and so on by means of grouping, cooperation achieves unity in form and content.

Evaluation criteria for experimental teaching of chemistry

First of all, students' understanding of chemistry comes in so many shapes and forms that it is impossible to each student should be properly assessed by quantitative methods, which will adopt an experiential method and the data must be shown and explained in order to be qualitatively evaluated. Second, according to the assessment procedure, the group should be assessed first to see who can and it is required of the teacher to gain the consent of more students in the group. Then by selecting the group to see whose results and will be recognized by more people in the class. Teachers also evaluate students' work. Finally, the teacher explained the evaluation criteria. For example, in this evaluation criteria experience includes internal standards and external standards and includes internal standards it is ensured that they have

complete information about the essence of chemistry, the level of novelty of the work and the content of the science. External standards include experimental attitudes, communication, operational standards, division of labor. Teachers play an important role in creating, implementing and reviewing and shows the results of the assessment standards.

Conclusions

Experiential learning based on cooperative learning takes into account the differences between students, creates an active learning environment for students and provides opportunities for students to learn. It links improved student engagement with more realistic academic practice and clear learning objectives in the laboratory, which is one of the most powerful methods of improvement grades, promote cognitive development, improve self-esteem, and improve interpersonal relationships relationships are reflected. In designing to achieve better experiential learning outcomes and implementation of cooperative learning activities, first of all, optimization of the group structure, the structure of tasks, learner roles and group norms, positive reciprocity, reward and evaluation mechanisms will need to be established. Students awareness of roles and cooperation needs to be strengthened. Second, by positive installation interdependence and individual responsibility, ensuring that each learner contributes and receives responsibility for learning, fully respects individual differences and gives play to everyone. Strengths are identified to balance the classroom structure. And finally, the group orientation of cooperative learning should be reduced as much as possible and the learning efficiency of different types of students should be increased and should be improved.

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